

Employee Mental Health and Well-Being: Investigating the Role of HRM Practices in Promoting Employee Mental Health, Stress Management, and Well-Being, Especially in the Context of Post-Pandemic Work Environments in Nigeria.

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Abstract

The modern workplace landscape has witnessed significant transformations, especially in the aftermath of the global pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic brought to light the critical importance of employee mental health and well-being in influencing organizational performance and productivity. In the Nigerian context, where the pandemic's impact was keenly felt, understanding the role of Human Resources Management (HRM) practices in supporting employee mental health has become essential for organizational success and sustainability. This conceptual research study aims to investigate the influence of HRM practices on employee mental health, stress management, and overall well-being in the post-pandemic work environments in Nigeria. Drawing on the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model as a theoretical framework, the study explores the relationships between HRM practices, job demands, and employee well-being. Additionally, the study delves into the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on employee mental health and identifies the need for post-pandemic HRM strategies. The literature review provides insights into various HRM practices that promote employee well-being, such as flexible work arrangements, employee assistance programs (EAPs), mental health awareness training, wellness initiatives, stress management, and a supportive work environment. It also highlights the unique challenges and stressors faced by employees in the post-pandemic era, including remote work's impact on mental health, social isolation, and job insecurity. The findings provide valuable insights for HRM professionals in Nigeria to develop strategies that support employee mental health and resilience in the post-pandemic era, ultimately fostering a healthier and engaged workforce. Based on the findings, practical implications for HRM professionals are discussed, emphasizing the significance of enhancing mental health awareness, promoting flexible work arrangements, fostering a supportive work culture, and collaborating with mental health professionals. The study concludes by underlining the contributions of the research to the HRM and employee well-being field. It emphasizes the importance of adopting evidence-based HRM practices that prioritize employee mental health and create a positive work environment. Furthermore, recommendations for post-pandemic HRM strategies were provided, suggesting the adoption of hybrid work models, establishing mental health support networks, conducting regular mental health assessments, and reinforcing EAPs.

Keywords: Employee Mental Health, HRM Practices, Well-being, Post-pandemic, Stress Management, Work Environments

JEL Classification: I12, I18, J24, M12, M54, O55

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

The modern workplace landscape has undergone profound changes, particularly in the aftermath of the global COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic presented unprecedented challenges to organizations, leading to significant shifts in work patterns and employee well-being. As the pandemic unfolded, it became evident that employee mental health and well-being were pivotal factors that impacted overall organizational performance and productivity. Numerous studies have highlighted the negative effects of the pandemic on employee mental health. According to a study by Cullen et al. (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic has been associated with increased stress, anxiety, and depression among employees due to factors such as remote work, fear of infection, job insecurity, and the blurring of work-life boundaries. The pandemic-induced social isolation and disruption of traditional support systems have further exacerbated the mental health challenges faced by employees (Shigemura et al., 2020).

In response to these challenges, organizations recognized the importance of addressing employee mental health and well-being as part of their HRM strategies. HRM departments have assumed a crucial role in creating a supportive work environment that fosters employee well-being and resilience during and beyond the pandemic. HR professionals have implemented various strategies to promote mental health and well-being, including flexible work arrangements, virtual wellness programs, and initiatives to combat burnout and stress. Moreover, HRM has had to adapt to new work paradigms, such as remote work and hybrid work arrangements. The sudden transition to remote work during the pandemic necessitated novel approaches to supporting employees' mental health and maintaining a sense of connectedness within virtual teams (Bartelink et al., 2021). Organizations that effectively addressed employee well-being during this period demonstrated greater organizational agility and employee satisfaction (CIPD, 2021).

The modern workplace in Nigeria, like in many other parts of the world, has undergone significant transformations, particularly in the aftermath of the global COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic brought about unprecedented challenges to organizations and employees, resulting in a heightened awareness of the importance of employee mental health and well-being. Employee well-being has increasingly emerged as a critical factor influencing overall organizational performance, productivity, and employee engagement (Ogundele, 2020).

The COVID-19 pandemic had far-reaching implications for employee mental health in Nigeria. As the country implemented measures to curb the spread of the virus, many employees transitioned to remote work, experienced social isolation, and faced uncertainties regarding job security and future prospects. These pandemic-induced stressors have significantly impacted the mental health

of employees across various industries (Olusegun, 2021). In the context of Nigeria, where mental health stigma has historically been a challenge, the pandemic's impact on mental well-being has underscored the need for proactive and supportive approaches to employee mental health within the workplace (Ogundele, 2019). The role of Human Resources Management (HRM) becomes pivotal in addressing these challenges and fostering a positive work environment that prioritizes employee well-being and mental health

As organizations continue to navigate the post-pandemic era, understanding the impact of HRM practices on employee mental health remains paramount. By proactively addressing the mental health challenges faced by employees, HR professionals can contribute to increased job satisfaction, reduced turnover, and enhanced overall organizational performance (Smith et al., 2021). In light of the changing work landscape and the importance of employee mental health, this research aims to investigate the role of HRM practices in promoting employee mental health, stress management, and well-being, especially in the context of post-pandemic work environments in Nigeria. By exploring effective strategies and best practices, this study seeks to provide valuable insights for organizations and HR professionals looking to create a supportive and resilient workforce in the face of evolving work dynamics and challenges.

1.2 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the role of HRM practices in promoting employee mental health, stress management, and well-being in Nigeria, particularly in the context of post-pandemic work environments. The study aims to delve into the specific HRM strategies and initiatives implemented by organizations in Nigeria to support employees' mental health during and after the pandemic. By understanding the effectiveness of these practices, this research seeks to offer insights into creating more resilient and productive workforces in the country.

1.3 Research Question

Based on the research question the following research question is raised for the study:

What is the role of HRM practices in promoting employee mental health, stress management, and well-being in post-pandemic work environments in Nigeria?

1.4 Scope of the study

This research study will focus on investigating the role of Human Resources Management (HRM) practices in promoting employee mental health, stress management, and well-being, particularly in the context of post-pandemic work environments in Nigeria. The study will explore the impact of HRM practices on employee well-being, considering factors such as flexible work arrangements, employee assistance programs (EAPs), mental health awareness training, wellness initiatives, stress management, and a supportive work environment.

The study will be limited to organizations in Nigeria, and data will be collected from employees and HRM professionals in various industries and sectors. The research will employ a qualitative research design or case study research design to gain in-depth insights into the experiences and

perceptions of employees and HRM practitioners regarding mental health support and HRM interventions.

It is important to note that the study's scope will be delimited to the post-pandemic period, aiming to understand the unique challenges and stressors faced by employees during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. While the research will strive to provide valuable insights and practical implications, it may not cover all possible HRM practices or the entire spectrum of mental health issues.

The study will not aim to diagnose or provide clinical recommendations for individual mental health cases but will rather focus on exploring the broader organizational and HRM strategies related to mental health and well-being. Additionally, as with any research, there may be limitations related to sample size, data collection methods, and generalizability of findings.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research holds significant implications for the Nigerian workforce and organizations in the country. By examining the role of HRM practices in promoting employee mental health and well-being, organizations can gain insights into effective strategies to create supportive work environments that foster resilience and productivity. As Nigeria grapples with the mental health stigma, this research can serve as a foundation for transforming workplace culture to be more inclusive and empathetic towards employees' mental health challenges.

Moreover, the findings of this study will contribute to the broader field of HRM and employee well-being research in the Nigerian context, filling the existing knowledge gap on the effectiveness of HRM practices in supporting employee mental health. Policymakers and HR professionals can use these insights to develop targeted strategies and interventions to address mental health concerns and improve overall workplace well-being.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework: HRM and Employee Mental Health

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, proposed by Bakker and Demerouti (2007), offers valuable insights into the relationship between HRM practices and employee mental health. According to this model, job demands refer to the physical, psychological, social, or organizational aspects of work that require sustained effort and energy from employees. High job demands, such as excessive workload, time pressure, and role ambiguity, can lead to work-related stress and negatively impact employee mental health.

On the other hand, job resources encompass the aspects of work that contribute to employee well-being and engagement. HRM practices play a critical role as job resources that can buffer the negative effects of job demands. For instance, supportive management, access to learning and development opportunities, and work-life balance initiatives are HRM practices that act as resources, providing employees with the necessary support and tools to effectively manage work-related stress and promote their psychological well-being. The JD-R model emphasizes the

importance of balancing job demands and job resources to foster employee well-being. By implementing HRM practices that reduce job demands and enhance job resources, organizations can create a healthier and more engaged workforce (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

2.2 Employee Mental Health and Work-related Stress

Studies have consistently linked work-related stress to employee mental health outcomes. Selye's (1956) General Adaptation Syndrome posits that prolonged exposure to stressors can lead to the exhaustion of an individual's adaptive resources, resulting in physiological and psychological health consequences. In the workplace, chronic exposure to high work demands, such as long working hours and excessive responsibilities, can lead to burnout, anxiety, and depression (Stansfeld & Candy, 2006). Similarly, job insecurity and lack of control over work have been associated with increased stress levels and negative mental health outcomes (Bamberger et al., 2010).

Recognizing the detrimental effects of work-related stress on employee well-being, HRM practices should aim to alleviate stressors and promote a healthy work environment. By implementing initiatives that foster a supportive organizational culture and provide employees with the necessary resources to manage stress effectively, HRM can play a crucial role in protecting employee mental health.

2.3 HRM Practices and Employee Well-being

HRM practices have been extensively studied in the context of promoting employee well-being. Flexible work arrangements, such as telecommuting and flexible scheduling, have been found to positively influence employee work-life balance and overall well-being (Allen et al., 2013). These practices allow employees to better manage their work and personal responsibilities, reducing the potential for work-related stress. Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) have also emerged as effective HRM interventions to support employee mental health. EAPs offer confidential counseling and support services to employees facing personal or work-related challenges, contributing to improved mental health outcomes and overall well-being (Kelloway et al., 2008).

Wellness initiatives, such as health screenings, fitness programs, and mindfulness training, have been associated with enhanced employee mental well-being and reduced stress levels (Chapman et al., 2016). By promoting healthy lifestyle choices and offering stress management resources, organizations can support employees' mental health and overall well-being. Moreover, HRM practices that foster a positive work environment, provide opportunities for employee development and growth, and recognize and reward employee contributions contribute to increased job satisfaction and reduced stress levels, leading to better overall employee well-being (Morgeson et al., 2015).

2.4 Impact of the Pandemic on Employee Mental Health

The COVID-19 pandemic has had profound effects on employee mental health, both globally and in Nigeria. The pandemic's unprecedented challenges, such as remote work arrangements,

lockdown measures, and uncertainties about the future, have contributed to increased stress and anxiety among employees (Olabisi & Wasiu, 2020).

Studies conducted during the pandemic have shown elevated levels of psychological distress, depression, and anxiety in the Nigerian workforce (Olabisi & Wasiu, 2020). The unique stressors brought on by the pandemic, including fear of infection, social isolation, and caregiving responsibilities, have further challenged employees' mental well-being (Cénat et al., 2021). Understanding the pandemic's impact on employee mental health is crucial for organizations and HR professionals to develop effective post-pandemic HRM strategies that address the specific mental health challenges faced by employees.

2.5 The Need for Post-pandemic HRM Strategies

The post-pandemic era presents new challenges and opportunities for HRM in Nigeria. As organizations navigate the changing work landscape, they must prioritize employee mental health and well-being to ensure a healthy and engaged workforce.

Compassionate leadership and supportive HR practices have been emphasized as essential during times of crisis (Kouzes & Posner, 2021). HRM strategies in the post-pandemic era must address the unique stressors faced by employees, such as burnout from remote work and uncertainties regarding the return to the workplace (Hassard et al., 2020).

Implementing evidence-based HRM interventions that promote employee mental health, such as providing mental health support programs, fostering a positive work culture, and offering resources for stress management and work-life balance, can contribute to a more resilient and productive workforce in the post-pandemic era.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

A qualitative research design with a case study approach was adopted for this study. Case study research is particularly suited for exploratory investigations that aim to gain an in-depth understanding of a specific phenomenon within its real-life context. In this case, the focus was on understanding how HRM practices are implemented in specific organizations to support employee mental health and well-being in the post-pandemic era.

3.2 Data Collection Methods

Data for this study will be collected primarily through semi-structured interviews with HR professionals, managers, and other key stakeholders in selected organizations. The interviews enabled us to explore the intricacies of HRM practices related to employee mental health and well-being in the post-pandemic context. Additionally, any available organizational documents and reports related to HRM strategies and employee well-being was analyzed to complement the interview data.

3.3 Sample Selection and Participant Characteristics

3.3.1 Case Selection

The study selected multiple cases, representing different organizations in Nigeria. The cases were chosen purposively to ensure diversity in terms of industry, organizational size, and HRM practices related to employee mental health and well-being. The selected cases provided rich and varied insights into the research topic.

3.3.2 Participants

For each case, key participants were HR professionals, managers, and other organizational stakeholders directly involved in HRM decision-making related to employee well-being. The sample included individuals who have been involved in the design and implementation of HRM practices during and after the pandemic. Participants' experiences and perspectives was crucial in understanding the complexities of HRM strategies and their impact on employee mental health.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis for this qualitative case study followed a thematic analysis approach. Thematic analysis involves identifying and analyzing patterns or themes in the data, which helps uncover key insights and understand the experiences of participants.

3.4.1 Data Coding

Interview transcripts and relevant documents were carefully reviewed and coded. Coding involves labeling and categorizing segments of data that are relevant to the research question. Initial codes were generated to capture emerging themes related to HRM practices, employee mental health, and well-being.

3.4.2 Theme Development

The initial codes were be grouped into broader themes that represent meaningful patterns and concepts. Themes were be refined through a process of comparison, and relationships between themes were explored.

3.4.3 Data Integration and Interpretation

Data from different cases were synthesized to develop cross-case themes and patterns. Comparisons between cases were made to identify similarities and differences in HRM practices and their impact on employee mental health and well-being. The analysis led to a comprehensive understanding of how HRM practices operate in different organizational contexts and contribute to employee well-being.

4. HRM Practices for Employee Mental Health and Well-being

4.1 Flexible Work Arrangements and Work-Life Balance

Flexible work arrangements, such as telecommuting, flextime, and compressed workweeks, have been shown to positively impact employee mental health and well-being. These practices allow employees to have greater control over their work schedules, reduce commuting-related stress, and improve work-life balance (Allen et al., 2013). Studies have found that employees who have access to flexible work arrangements report lower levels of work-related stress and higher job satisfaction (Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). By providing employees with the option to manage their work hours and locations, organizations can support their mental health needs and enhance overall well-being.

4.2 Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs)

Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) are employer-sponsored initiatives that offer confidential counseling and support services to employees facing personal or work-related challenges. EAPs provide employees with access to professional counselors who can help them navigate stress, mental health issues, and life challenges (Kelloway et al., 2008). Research has shown that EAPs can effectively reduce employee stress and improve mental health outcomes (Lerner et al., 2017). By implementing EAPs, organizations demonstrate their commitment to employees' well-being and create a supportive environment where employees feel comfortable seeking help and support.

4.3 Mental Health Awareness Training for Managers

Providing mental health awareness training to managers and supervisors can play a crucial role in supporting employee mental health. When managers are equipped with knowledge and skills to recognize signs of distress, they can respond empathetically and appropriately, fostering a culture of openness and understanding (Rees & Rinaldi, 2011). Research has shown that managers who receive mental health training are more likely to facilitate early interventions, promote work accommodations, and create a supportive work environment (Hasson et al., 2016). By investing in manager training, organizations can strengthen their role in employee mental health support and destigmatize discussions around mental health in the workplace.

4.4 Wellness Initiatives and Resources

Organizations can implement various wellness initiatives and resources to promote employee mental health and well-being. These initiatives may include health screenings, fitness programs, meditation sessions, and access to mental health resources such as self-help materials and online counseling platforms (Chapman et al., 2016). Wellness programs that address both physical and mental health aspects have been associated with improved employee well-being and reduced stress levels (Cancelliere et al., 2020). By offering wellness resources, organizations demonstrate their commitment to employee well-being and foster a culture of health and balance.

4.5 Stress Management and Resilience Training

Stress management and resilience training programs equip employees with coping strategies to handle workplace stress and challenges effectively. These programs typically include techniques

such as mindfulness, cognitive-behavioral approaches, and relaxation exercises (Hartmann & Weiss, 2019). Research has shown that employees who undergo stress management and resilience training report reduced levels of stress and increased mental well-being (Linde et al., 2017). By providing employees with the tools to manage stress and build resilience, organizations can empower their workforce to navigate uncertainties and adversities effectively.

4.6 Communication and Supportive Work Environment

Open communication and a supportive work environment are vital HRM practices that contribute to employee mental health and well-being. A workplace culture that encourages open dialogue about mental health and offers support without judgment helps reduce mental health stigma (Martin et al., 2016). Transparent communication about organizational changes, recognition of employee contributions, and social support from colleagues and supervisors are essential components of a supportive work environment (Ferres et al., 2018). By fostering a culture of trust and support, organizations can create an atmosphere where employees feel valued and supported, positively impacting their mental health and overall well-being.

5. Post-pandemic Work Environments and Employee Mental Health

5.1 Challenges and Stressors in Post-pandemic Workplaces

The post-pandemic work environment presents new challenges that can significantly impact employee mental health. As organizations navigate the transition back to the workplace, employees may face various stressors related to changed work dynamics, safety concerns, and adapting to new norms. Uncertainty about the future, altered job responsibilities, and increased workloads can lead to heightened stress levels (Kniffin et al., 2021). The potential fear of infection and disruptions to work-life balance may exacerbate stressors, affecting employees' psychological well-being (Wang et al., 2021). Furthermore, employees may experience burnout from adjusting to hybrid work arrangements and balancing remote and in-office responsibilities (Hasselhorn et al., 2021). Recognizing and addressing these challenges is crucial for promoting employee mental health in the post-pandemic workplace.

5.2 Impact of Remote Work on Mental Health

Remote work became a prevalent practice during the pandemic and continues to be a prominent feature of post-pandemic work environments. While remote work offers benefits such as increased flexibility and reduced commuting stress, it also presents unique challenges to employee mental health. Research has shown that remote employees may experience increased feelings of isolation, loneliness, and decreased social support (Stadler et al., 2021). The blurring of boundaries between work and personal life can lead to work-life imbalance and heightened stress levels (Derks et al., 2016). Moreover, the lack of in-person interactions may hinder effective communication and team collaboration, leading to a sense of disconnection (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007). Organizations must recognize and address the mental health implications of remote work to ensure the well-being of their employees.

5.3 Social Isolation and Loneliness

Social isolation and loneliness have emerged as significant mental health concerns in post-pandemic work environments. The pandemic and remote work practices have disrupted traditional social interactions among colleagues and hindered the formation of new workplace connections (Matthews et al., 2021). Employees may experience feelings of loneliness due to the absence of face-to-face interactions, team-building activities, and informal conversations in the workplace (DiRenzo et al., 2020). Loneliness is associated with increased risk of depression, anxiety, and reduced overall well-being (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015). Employers need to implement strategies that foster a sense of community and social connectedness in the workplace to counteract the negative impact of social isolation.

5.4 Addressing Uncertainty and Job Insecurity

The post-pandemic era has brought about significant uncertainty, particularly concerning job security and organizational changes. Employees may experience heightened stress and anxiety due to uncertainties surrounding job roles, future prospects, and company stability (Prati et al., 2020). Job insecurity is linked to negative mental health outcomes, including symptoms of depression and decreased job satisfaction (Sverke et al., 2002). Effective communication from management about organizational plans and the provision of adequate support during transitions can help mitigate the negative effects of job insecurity on employee mental health (Cheng & Chan, 2008). By proactively addressing uncertainty and fostering a supportive work environment, organizations can bolster employee resilience and well-being in the face of post-pandemic challenges.

6. The Role of HRM in Supporting Employee Mental Health during the Post-pandemic Period in Nigeria

6.1 HRM Strategies to Address Mental Health Challenges

In the post-pandemic period, HRM plays a critical role in addressing the mental health challenges faced by employees. Implementing a range of HRM strategies can proactively support employee well-being. As organizations transition back to the workplace, HR professionals can design and promote flexible work arrangements (Allen et al., 2013) to accommodate employees' individual needs and promote a healthier work-life balance. Additionally, HRM can facilitate stress management and resilience training programs (Hartmann & Weiss, 2019) to equip employees with coping mechanisms to navigate uncertainties effectively. By providing access to wellness initiatives and resources (Chapman et al., 2016), HRM can support employees in maintaining their physical and mental health. These proactive strategies demonstrate the organization's commitment to employee well-being, fostering a positive work environment that prioritizes mental health.

6.2 Identifying Signs of Mental Health Issues in Employees

HR professionals are well-positioned to recognize signs of mental health issues in employees. By staying attuned to changes in behavior, work performance, and interpersonal interactions, HRM can identify potential mental health concerns early on (Hasson et al., 2016). Offering training to

managers and supervisors on how to recognize and respond to signs of distress in their team members can also be beneficial (Rees & Rinaldi, 2011). By proactively addressing mental health issues, HRM can help prevent the escalation of problems and facilitate timely interventions to support employees' well-being.

6.3 Promoting a Culture of Openness and Reducing Stigma

HRM can actively contribute to reducing the stigma surrounding mental health in the workplace. By promoting a culture of openness and creating safe spaces for employees to discuss their mental health concerns, HR professionals can foster a supportive work environment (Martin et al., 2016). Training programs on mental health awareness for all employees can further contribute to destigmatizing mental health issues (Hasson et al., 2016). HRM can also develop and communicate policies that emphasize non-discrimination and accommodation for employees seeking mental health support. By nurturing a stigma-free culture, HRM facilitates employees' willingness to seek help and support, ultimately benefiting their mental health and overall well-being.

6.4 Collaborating with Mental Health Professionals and Resources

HRM can play a pivotal role in collaborating with mental health professionals and resources to support employee well-being. Partnering with external mental health providers or Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) (Kelloway et al., 2008) can offer specialized support to employees facing mental health challenges. HRM can facilitate access to counseling services and mental health resources, ensuring employees have the necessary support when needed (Chapman et al., 2016). Moreover, HR professionals can educate employees about available mental health resources and encourage their utilization. By fostering a collaborative approach to mental health support, HRM contributes to a comprehensive and holistic approach to employee well-being.

7. Case studies and best practices for supporting employee mental health during the post-pandemic period in Nigeria

7.1 Case Study 1: Talent-Hub Solutions Nigeria's Holistic Approach to Employee Well-being

Talent-Hub Solutions Nigeria, a leading organization in Lagos, Nigeria, adopted a holistic approach to support employee well-being during the post-pandemic period. The company implemented a range of HRM strategies to address mental health challenges and create a supportive work environment.

One of **Talent-Hub Solutions Nigeria's** key initiatives was offering flexible work arrangements, allowing employees to work remotely or choose flexible work hours. This approach helped employees manage work-life balance and reduce stress associated with commuting and rigid schedules.

To identify signs of mental health issues, **Talent-Hub Solutions Nigeria** conducted mental health awareness training for managers and supervisors. Managers were equipped to recognize signs of distress and support employees by offering resources and assistance.

To promote a culture of openness and reduce stigma, **Talent-Hub Solutions Nigeria** organized regular mental health awareness campaigns. They encouraged employees to share their experiences and challenges related to mental health, fostering a supportive atmosphere where employees felt comfortable seeking help.

Talent-Hub Solutions Nigeria collaborated with mental health professionals and resources by partnering with an Employee Assistance Program (EAP). Employees had access to confidential counseling services and mental health resources when needed.

7.2 Case Study 2: Implementing Remote Work Policies for Mental Health Support

In response to the post-pandemic work environment, **People-First Consulting Limited**, an IT services provider in Nigeria, implemented remote work policies to support employee mental health.

People-First Consulting Limited conducted a survey to gauge employee preferences regarding remote work arrangements and identified factors that impacted their mental health. Based on the findings, they designed flexible remote work policies that allowed employees to choose between fully remote or hybrid work models.

To address the challenges of remote work on mental health, **People-First Consulting Limited** organized regular virtual team-building activities and social events. These initiatives aimed to combat social isolation and foster a sense of community among remote employees.

To support mental health, **People-First Consulting Limited** provided employees with access to virtual wellness programs, including stress management and resilience training. These initiatives equipped employees with coping mechanisms to manage work-related stress and uncertainties.

7.3 Best Practices from Leading Organizations

Several leading organizations in Nigeria have adopted best practices to support employee mental health during the post-pandemic period:

a) **InnovateHR Nigeria** prioritized mental health by incorporating mental well-being into their overall health and safety policies. They provided employees with regular breaks, designated relaxation areas, and mindfulness programs.

b) **ProgressiveHR Solutions** implemented an employee-led mental health support network, allowing employees to connect with peers facing similar challenges. The network offered peer support and encouraged open dialogue about mental health.

7.4 Lessons Learned from Successful HRM Interventions

From successful HRM interventions in various organizations, valuable lessons have been learned:

- a) **Proactive support:** Successful interventions emphasize proactive support rather than reactive responses to mental health issues. Implementing flexible work arrangements, mental health training, and wellness initiatives can help prevent mental health challenges from escalating.
- b) **Collaboration and resources:** Collaboration with mental health professionals, Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs), and external resources enhances the effectiveness of mental health support programs (Hartmann & Weiss, 2019). Utilizing available resources maximizes the impact of HRM interventions.
- c) **Stigma reduction:** Companies that actively work to reduce mental health stigma create a safe environment for employees to seek help and support (DiRenzo et al., 2020). Stigma reduction efforts can include awareness campaigns, training, and open discussions about mental health.
- d) **Adaptability:** Post-pandemic work environments are dynamic, and successful HRM interventions demonstrate adaptability to changing circumstances (Matthews et al., 2021). Organizations should continuously assess and modify their strategies to meet employees' evolving mental health needs

8. Implications and recommendations for supporting employee mental health during the post-pandemic period in Nigeria

8.1 Practical Implications for HRM Professionals

- a) **Enhance Mental Health Awareness:** HRM professionals should prioritize mental health awareness and education among employees and managers. Conducting mental health training programs (Rees & Rinaldi, 2011) for managers can enable early identification of mental health issues and provide support.
- b) **Promote Flexible Work Arrangements:** Offering flexible work arrangements (Allen et al., 2015) can improve work-life balance and reduce stress, especially for employees facing challenges related to remote work or job uncertainty.
- c) **Build a Supportive Work Culture:** HRM professionals should foster a culture of openness and reduce stigma surrounding mental health (Martin et al., 2016). Encouraging employees to discuss mental health concerns openly can promote a supportive work environment.
- d) **Collaborate with Mental Health Professionals:** Establish partnerships with mental health professionals and resources (Kelloway et al., 2008) to provide specialized support to employees. Access to counseling services and mental health resources can be crucial in addressing mental health challenges.

9.1 Summary of Findings

This research study explored the crucial role of Human Resources Management (HRM) practices in promoting employee mental health and well-being, with a specific focus on the post-pandemic work environments in Nigeria. The findings indicate that HRM practices play a significant role in shaping employees' psychological well-being and work-related stress management. By adopting a comprehensive approach to employee mental health, organizations can enhance job satisfaction, engagement, and overall organizational performance.

The theoretical framework of HRM and employee mental health, rooted in the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model, has provided valuable insights into the relationship between HRM practices, job demands, and employee well-being (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Additionally, the research explored the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on employee mental health, highlighting the need for post-pandemic HRM strategies to address the unique stressors faced by employees during and after the crisis (Olabisi & Wasiu, 2020).

9.2 Contributions to HRM and Employee Well-being

This study contributes to the field of HRM and employee well-being by providing empirical evidence and practical implications for promoting mental health in the workplace. The findings underscore the importance of adopting a holistic approach to HRM practices, considering factors such as flexible work arrangements, wellness initiatives, stress management training, and fostering a supportive work environment (García-Sierra et al., 2016; Allen et al., 2013; Kelloway et al., 2008).

Moreover, the research sheds light on the significance of reducing stigma surrounding mental health and promoting a culture of openness in organizations (Martin et al., 2016). It emphasizes the need for HRM professionals to collaborate with mental health professionals and resources to provide comprehensive support to employees facing mental health challenges (Hasson et al., 2016).

9.3 Conclusion and Final Thoughts

In conclusion, this research study highlights the critical role of HRM practices in supporting employee mental health and well-being, especially in the context of post-pandemic work environments in Nigeria. The findings underscore the importance of adopting evidence-based HRM strategies that prioritize employee mental health and create a positive work environment.

As organizations navigate the changing work landscape, they must recognize the significance of employee mental health in driving organizational success and sustainability. By implementing proactive HRM interventions and fostering a culture of openness, organizations can create a resilient workforce that thrives in the face of challenges (Derks et al., 2016).

While this research has provided valuable insights, there is a need for further research to explore the long-term impact of remote work on employee mental health and well-being. Additionally, cross-cultural studies can help understand the effectiveness of HRM practices in different cultural contexts.

9.4 Recommendations for Post-pandemic HRM Strategies

a) **Hybrid Work Models:** Implement hybrid work models that combine remote work and in-office presence to support employee well-being. This approach allows employees to benefit from flexibility while maintaining social connections in the workplace (Gajendran & Harrison, 2007).

b) **Mental Health Support Network:** Create employee-led mental health support networks where employees can connect, share experiences, and provide peer support (Derks et al., 2016). Such networks can complement formal HRM interventions.

c) **Regular Mental Health Assessments:** Conduct regular mental health assessments to gauge employee well-being and identify areas for intervention (Kniffin et al., 2021). Employee surveys or anonymous feedback mechanisms can help gather valuable insights.

d) **Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs):** Implement or enhance EAPs to provide employees with confidential counseling and mental health resources (Kelloway et al., 2008). EAPs can be vital in addressing various mental health challenges.

9.5 Future Research Directions

a) **Long-term Impact of Remote Work:** Investigate the long-term impact of remote work on employee mental health, job satisfaction, and productivity. Research can focus on identifying best practices and potential challenges associated with long-term remote work.

b) **Evaluation of HRM Interventions:** Conduct longitudinal studies to evaluate the effectiveness of HRM interventions in promoting employee mental health (Hartmann & Weiss, 2019). Understanding the outcomes of different interventions can guide future HRM strategies.

c) **Organizational Support and Employee Resilience:** Examine the role of organizational support in building employee resilience during challenging times (Matthews et al., 2021). Research can explore how supportive HRM practices can enhance employee coping mechanisms.

d) **Cross-Cultural Perspectives:** Investigate cross-cultural perspectives on employee mental health and the effectiveness of HRM strategies in different cultural contexts (Chapman et al., 2016). Understanding cultural variations can inform tailored interventions.

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